

Post-Pandemic Travel Behaviour in Uttarakhand State: Reverse Migration Can be Effective Tool for Rural Tourism Kick Start in India

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ABSTRACT

The Corona Virus Pandemic has awfully impacted tourism sector. Tourism in Uttarakhand has been on knee with scores of people working for this sector are now facing the problem of jobless situation as there is a nationwide lockdown to halt the spread of the deadly virus. All the tourism spots and also Char Dham Yatra have been suffered losses this year. Many hotels and restaurants are on the verge of closing due to the lockdown. Government is working on a plan to revive tourism, which is leading revenue-earning sector of the state. According to tourism vice president Mr. Vijay, there are 20 to 25 lakh people who are involved in tourism and travel directly affected due to corona period. As no one knows how long this global pandemic will last, so administration should ere on the side of caution in their strategic communications and identify how the needs and demand will change post-pandemic travel behaviour. Uttarakhand was facing a great challenge of migration since last decade, only positive effect due to covid-19 is that thousands of migrants who had left Uttarakhand returning their own villages. This can be great opportunity to the state to rebuild their lives to set up rural tourism, eco-tourism and micro-enterprises.

Post-Pandemic Travel Behaviour

The simple approach for travel industry that will need to understand how tourist and travel behaviour will inevitably change as a result of pandemic. Government of state and industry should focus on their efforts on:

- Lifting travel restrictions with new health protocol for safe travel and help to diversify the travel market.
- Restore traveller confidence and stimulate demand with new safe and sanitize labels for tourism promotion campaigns.
- Prepare comprehensive tourism recovery plans, to redevelop the destinations and the strategy implementation.

These essential actions should be taken, to reopen the economy of tourism and to run it more needs to be done in cooperative way as tourism services are very interdependent. Government authority should notably focus the workers and labourers related with travel industry. Drivers, bellboy, waiters, tourist escorts, guides, coolies, Trek leaders these need particular attention. Demand side recovery obviously will take some time, while the tourism consumer confidence and travel behaviour is deeply impacted the longer time. Domestic tourism is expected to be effective tool in

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initial recovery phase, Uttarakhand already represents a significant share of domestic tourism. As one of the major pilgrimage tourism spot Uttarakhand receives large number of pilgrims every year. Now the time has come for new promotion policy specially focused on health and hygiene protocol for safe tourism. Opening up the industry again is going to be more difficult than shutting it down. A widespread collapse of SMEs is the strong impact on state economy and growth prospects. Tourism services are often interdependent and collapse in one sub-sector, this can be disastrous follow on another dependent sector. A major challenge as the sector looks to reopen and how to get all interlinked supply chain will work together again. To revive the tourism sector in the state, government authority and industry key players should be aware of some travel behaviour changes:

- Mass tourism was one of major feature of Uttarakhand tourism, now it seems to end up so the time to make strategy to manage social distancing during pilgrimage tour.
- Health and hygiene standards will be now mainstream.
- Time to promote rural and health tourism with new features and scheme special context with covid-19.
- Quarantine and isolation tourism can be promoted, Uttarakhand has so many abandoned villages with healthy environment and peaceful climate to improve health.
- Develop 'Alternative Tourism' in response of covid-19.

We haven't seen a global crisis that's impacted globally and every country of the tourism industry, To be sure, the tourism industry has traditionally shown considerable resilience in rebounding after many crises and disasters. Commonly, this recovery has been come through the intervention of local, regional and national governments, which create an environment whereby, in the prevailing spirit of neoliberalism, they entice investors through a series of incentives (tax breaks, lifting of stringent land use regulations, etc.) (Brouder, 2020).

Remigration can be effective tool for rural tourism:

Over the years, Himalayan state Uttarakhand has seen large exodus of people to the plains, different part of the country and abroad because of lack of opportunity and poor development in the hills area. Now, the manufacturing units, hotels, and other business widespread closure has forced them to return. As April 2020, a total of 59,360 people has returned. Between 2001 to 2011, about 1100 villages totally uninhabited and after 2011 as many as 734 more villages have become ghost village because of mass migration. The return of the migrants has breathed fresh life in to many ghost villages, villages are looking lively again as many have begun ploughing their fields. About 60-65 % people who have returned, came back states such as Haryana, Punjab, Goa and Tamilnadu, and 25-30 % came from the urban packets in Uttarakhand like as Dehradun, Haridwar, Udham Singh Nagar; and rest of the migrants from other countries such as Dubai, Australia and Oman (RDMC report, 2020).

Table 1. Immigrants from Countries

SN	Name of District	Number of Reverse Migrants
1.	Almora	9303
2.	Bageshwar	1541
3.	Chamoli	3214
4.	Champawat	5707
5.	Nainital	4771
6.	Pauri	12039
7.	Pithoragarh	5035

8.	Rudraprayag	4247
9.	Tehri	8782
10.	Uttarkashi	4721
	Total	59360

Source : (Rural, 2020) Development and Migration Commission, April.

This table shows the district wise reverse migrants till April, 2020. A large number of returnees are 30-45 years old and work largely for the hospitality sector at low pay. It is a great opportunity for the government authorities to reach out of its skilled and experienced reverse migrants. It is needed to take a initiative and additional budget for employment generating schemes in for rural development. State government can relaunch 'Veer Chandra Garhwali Yojna' with the context of covid-19 pandemic, which offers micro credit aimed to create sustainable employment opportunities in tourism services and facilities.

Table 2. The District Wise Reverse Migrants till April, 2020.

District	Less than 25 years (%)	26-35 years (%)	Over 35 years (%)
Uttarkashi	30.68	36.56	32.77
Chamoli	26.71	43.49	29.79
Rudraprayag	28.97	41.83	29.20
Tehri Garhwal	29.26	40.92	29.82
Pauri Garhwal	29.23	41.67	29.10
Pithoragarh	28.32	42.58	29.10
Bageshwar	33.92	42.10	23.97
Almora	29.19	42.22	28.59
Nainital	29.48	44.57	25.96

Source: (Rural, 2020), Development and Migration Commission, Uttarakhand

Most of the returnees are between 25-45 age group, this group have skill and experience in different fields but according to Rural Development and Migration Commission (RDMC) number of reverse migrants are related with hospitality sector, these people have experience work with hotels, restaurants, transport in different part of India. Now the time to utilize their skills in home state, by the additional budget and initiative, state can change the whole scenario after covid-19 period. These villagers looking for job opportunity and state wants to stop migration, so collaboration between manpower and government authority will be a new kick start for rural tourism in Uttarakhand.

Conclusion

Across the globe nobody had foreseen the horrible period of covid19 outbreak, not only industries and tourism sector, even the largest economies have failed to deal with pandemic. Uttarakhand state was facing the problem of migration and lack of skilled manpower for development programme, but when number of skilled workers have returned to their villages, abandoned village's life come back again, so the time for authorities to take an initiative to maintain the rural livelihood once again. Lockdown period should be considered as the preparation period for the relaunching of rural tourism with the context of post pandemic travel behaviour.

REFERENCES

- Brouder, P. (2020). Reset Redux: possible evolutionary pathways towards the transformation of tourism in a COVID-19 world. *Tourism Geographies*. <https://doi:10.1080/14616688.2020.1760928> [Google Scholar]
- Chanel, S. (2020, April 15). 'It's catastrophic': Fiji's colossal tourism sector devastated by coronavirus. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/apr/16/its-catastrophic-fijis-colossal-tourism-sector-devastated-by-coronavirus> [Google Scholar]
- Glusac, E. (2020, April 15). "How will COVID-19 affect future travel behavior? A travel crisis expert explains". *New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/04/15/travel/q-and-a-coronavirus-travel.html?action=click&module=Features&pgtype=Homepage> [Google Scholar]
- Kumar, Sanjeev (2020, April 29), Uttarakhand Discusses Measures to Ensure Returning Migrant Workers Stay Permanently, <https://thewire.in/government/uttarakhand-discusses-measures-to-ensure-returning-migrant-workers-stay-permanently>.
- Rural Development and migration commission of Uttarakhand , April 2020, <http://www.uttarakhandpalayanayog.com/>
- Verma, Lalmani (2020, April 20) In Covid-19 crisis, Uttarakhand sees 'reverse migration' opportunity, <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/in-covid-19-crisis-uttarakhand-sees-reverse-migration-opportunity-6370059/>.